

Report on nextGEMS Challenge Problems

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For the hackathon we built teams advised by consultants from the renewable energy sector to address specific challenges:

- **Challenge 1:** What is the minimal amount of information needed to optimize the design of a regional renewable energy system and how can we extract this information from global storm-resolving models.
- **Challenge 2:** How does the potential renewable energy output landscape change with a changing climate?

The teams were provided with meteogram station data of wind speed at 100 m (V) above the surface, surface diffuse (D) and direct solar radiation (S), from two different models. Along with temporally sparse snapshots of full three dimensional model output. Their job was to either find a condensation of the high-frequency output (V, D, S), or suggest other output variables, to support the design of renewable energy systems.

Teams were supported by technical consultants (members of the modelling groups) to help them understand the model output and ways of accessing it. This worked very well, and the feedback from participants was generally positive. They mostly used the example scripts that were provided and then rewrote them to their specific needs. This way participants could focus on the science rather than solving technical problems.

Additionally, the teams were supported by energy consultants, to for instance help them understand design parameters (hub height, diffuse versus direct efficiency, etc.). In particular we had two sessions with Iberdrola and with Vestas Wind Systems. These sessions were particularly useful for the participants to understand the problems that the energy industry is facing, and provided an opportunity to discuss their results with experts. There was also a discussion of how the participants potentially develop a career in the renewable energy sector (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Expert interacting with hackathon participant.

Findings during the hackathon

The approach taken in the hackathon is to use the ability of the nextGEMS models to resolve the mesoscales and represent relevant motion and fields for renewable energy production. We used primarily dedicated high frequency output for a series of stations, but also the complete mapped output.

For example the wind at rotor height of a typical wind power plant around 100 m above ground is used directly to calculate the power output from a typical turbine. The below image shows how the output depends on the wind speed. The output starts at a minimum wind speed and increases with the wind speed to the third power up to a maximum value which is limited by the generator size. At high wind speeds the turbines automatically turn off to limit wear and for safety reasons (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Power output curve.

Because the power output curve is highly non-linear in the wind speed, we were interested in seeing how much estimated power is biased if using lower temporal resolution. Figure 3 shows output for four different stations. First we note that estimated output is monotonically decreasing with lower resolution suggesting that all stations, except perhaps the EUREC4A ocean site, are mostly seeing winds on the cubic wind speed range. For this a different combination of turbine, generator and tower height can be used to extract more energy at these sites. We also see that the bias is very low when degrading from 3 minute to 1 hour means, and even monthly mean wind speeds provide a reasonable estimate. Here it is important to note that this is the average of the instantaneous wind speed. If the wind components were average the degradation would be much larger.

Figure 3: Power output at different stations at different resolutions.

Finally, we checked how the models perform in terms of representing the observed wind speed at the flat surface Cabauw site in the Netherlands. It turns out that both the IFS and ICON grossly underestimates the occurrence of high wind speeds. For wind speeds above 10 m/s by a factor of two or more. Naturally, this comes at the expense of having weaker winds than 5 m/s far too often (Fig. 4a).

This bias in both the IFS and the standard ICON-Sapphire setup is related to the parameterisation of turbulent drag. This can be seen from the 10 km resolution test simulation conducted using the TTE scheme, which exhibits a more realistic distribution at Cabauw (Fig. 4b).

Figure 4: Modelled wind speed at Cabauw.

We next turn to solar power generation. The below plot shows a comparison of the monthly mean modelled downwelling shortwave radiation with observations at the Cabauw site. Here both IFS and ICON do a good job in predicting the observations. Also, the IFS model was analysed in three different resolutions but there is no obvious difference (Fig. 5).

Figure 5: Monthly mean downwelling shortwave radiation.

To convert the downwelling shortwave radiation to power output one must take into account various losses, here assumed to amount to 12 percent, as well as the temperature degradation, here assumed to be $-0.5\%/K$. Left panel shows a map from ICON of the solar energy reaching the surface in kW hours per year. To the right the maximum which can be extracted with such panels. We see that although there is a lot of radiation available in the sub-tropics, e.g. the Sahara, much of this advantage is counteracted by the warm temperatures (Fig. 6).

Figure 6: Solar energy reaching the surface in kWh/a.

Finally, we investigated whether wind and solar power can be combined at so-called hybrid sites. At such sites one combines multiple sources of energy, as well as energy storage or renewable fuel generation, to be able to improve the match between supply and demand. The figure shows the annual cycle of wind power generation from two regions. Whereas Oklahoma exhibits nearly no annual cycle, wind power output from a site near Cabauw in the Netherlands varies about a factor three between minima in summer and maxima in winter. Since solar panel output (see above) at this site varies in the opposite sense, and by roughly the same order of magnitude it seems feasible to combine the two types of power there (Fig. 7).

Figure 7: Annual cycle of wind power generation.

Challenges for the renewable energy industry

What became clear through the hackathon was that the wind industry is already working with quite advanced modelling tools for site planning and short term forecasting of wind power, along with on site observations. The situation is slightly less advanced for solar power, partly because the modelling tools are not nearly of the same quality due to problems with modelling clouds. New demands on the industry to also assess the impact of the changing climate on production, safety and durability/maintenance needs is a challenge that the industry is not well suited to meet, and where more research is urgently needed. Also, industry is looking forward to leveraging DestinationEarth digital twin simulations in their workflow.